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Pushing the boundaries for asphalt recycling in surface layers

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- ❖ **Cracking-Based Brittleness Index - CBI approach**
- ❖ **Level 1: RA screening/assessment**
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Pushing for more recycling, why?

❖ Economical + environmental drives

- Increase (re)use of reclaimed asphalt (RA)
(also in surface layers)
- Circular economy paradigm

❖ Ok, let's recycle more!

- Impact of more recycling on durability of bituminous mixtures

Source: Rli, *Circular Economy: From Wish to Practice*

Background - Goal

- **(More) RA in surface layers**
 - All RA materials suitable?
 - Durability concerns when include (high content) RA in surface layers?
- Need for a framework to detect risky RA materials & risky mixtures with RA
- Level 1 (RA level): RA characterization (CBI)
 - Level 2 (Mix level): Balanced-Mix Design (BMD) approach

Cracking-Based Brittleness Index-CBI

- **RA ageing state (current practice):**
 - Based on recovered RA binder properties (pen or $T_{R\&B}$)
- **Alternative: CBI as a solvent-free “mechanistic test”** → captures bulk (RA) response
- Indirect tensile test (IDT) principle
- Specimens made of 100% RA
 - 7% air voids target
- Higher CBI values indicate more brittle mixture

Level 1: RA characterization - *CBI results*

- **Several RA materials tested**
 - pen ranging from 7 to 20 (0,1 mm)
 - RA “further aged”(denoted FA)
- **Generally ranking reflects well “binder ageing”**
 - RA E1 and RA D FA : very aged binders show highest value
 - RA D and E2 : less aged, highest pen , lowest CBI
 - AC 10 ref (unaged) the lowest

Scan Me

Level 2: Mix level - *BMD approach*

- **6 RA materials tested in AC-10 surf**
 - 50% RA-binder replacement
- **Balanced-Mix Design (BMD) approach:**
 - **Compactability assessment: voids @ 60 gyrations – EN 12697-31**
 - **Cracking resistance: SCB + IDT test**
 - **Rutting resistance @ 50°C – EN 12697-22**
 - **Additional performance assessment:**
 - Water sensitivity : EN126987-12 + 23
 - Raveling: CEN- TS 12697- 50

Level 2: Mix level - *Compactability assessment*

- **AC 10 surf: 3–8% void (Flemish requirement)**
- **5 mixtures with 50% RA meet requirement**
- **3 risky mixtures:**
 - Mix with 50% RA D + RA E1 FA exhibited over-compaction
 - Mix with 50% RA C (marginally) exceeded the upper limit
- **Different RA's may introduce compaction risk**

Level 2: Mix level - *Rutting resistance assessment*

- **AC 10 surf: < 10% rut depth (Flemish requirement)**
- **Rutting resistance: no risks (< 10%)**
 - AC surf + RA : Better than ref mix (stiffer)
 - No rutting risks (for the designed/studied mixes)

Level 2: Mix level - *Cracking resistance (IDT + SCB)*

▪ Semi-Circular Bending (SCB)

- SCB samples:
 - H=75mm – W=150mm – 7% air voids
 - Notch: 10 mm (depth) – 1,8 mm (width)
- Test conditions
 - 15°C
 - 5 mm/min
- Analysis approach:
 - CRI

$$CRI = \frac{G_f}{P_{max}}$$

▪ Indirect tensile test (IDT)

- IDT samples:
 - D=150mm – H=66mm – 7% air voids
- Test parameters
 - 25°C
 - 50 mm/min
- Analysis approach:
 - CRI

Level 2: Mix level - Cracking resistance (IDT + SCB)

- Higher CRI → higher cracking resistance
 - AC ref: highest CRI
 - Mixes with RA ranking:
 - RA D: less aged, highest CRI
 - RA E1 and E1-FA: most aged, lowest CRI
 - SCB more discriminative, mixes with RA less (cracking) resistant
- Good agreement between CBI and CRI

Level 2: Mix level – *other performance requirements*

- **Water sensitivity:**
 - AC surf : ITS-R > 80% (Flemish requirement)
 - All mixes > 80%
- **Raveling**
 - DSD – 25°C – 2 kN – 50 cycles
 - studied mixtures quite resistant (< 120 g/m²)
 - even with the inclusion of a very aged RA material (RA E1)

General take-away points

- **2-level framework to evaluate durability of surface layer mixtures with inclusion of (high %) RA**
- **Level 1: RA characterization (100 % RA)**
 - **CBI → a solvent-free method**; captures **global response** of RA-material
 - **Higher CBI → RA materials with more brittle** behaviour & **higher ageing severity**
- **Level 2: BMD Performance approach on mix level (50% RA inclusion)**
 - No (or limited) risks detected for water sensitivity, rutting, and raveling
 - **Risky mixtures identified** regarding compactability and cracking resistance

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